

An Evaluation of the Implementation of the Model of Integrated Care for Type 2 Diabetes in two Community Health Organizations

PEOPLE WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES TOPIC GUIDE

- Thank participant, introduce who researcher is
- Refer to information sheet/consent form they have received and ask if they have any questions
- Ask again for permission to record interview and the reason why it is being recorded
- Remind them again of purpose of the interview (their experiences of attending the diabetes integrated care team) to see if service can be improved.

Topic	Prompts
<p>Introduction <i>(informed by responses to patient questionnaire)</i></p> <p>You have been attending (insert relevant HCP) for your diabetes care for (insert timeline) and were referred to this HCP by (insert relevant HCP). Is that right?</p>	
<p>Accessibility of attending integrated care diabetes service</p> <p>Can you tell me a little bit more about attending this service?</p> <p>Positive/negative experience? (in what way)</p> <p>Have you attended another HCP like this HCP in the past?</p> <p>Yes/No If Yes, where?</p> <p>How would you compare this service with previous service?</p>	<p><i>(Depending on response to general question prompt regarding)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waiting times to attend the service - Travel time to attend the service - Waiting times on the day of appointment - Length of time of appointment - Anything else you: Liked/disliked about attending the service
<p>HCP knowledge of your condition at first visit?</p> <p>Did you think she/he had the most up to date information on your diabetes when you saw her/him for the first time?</p> <p>Yes/No (Can you tell me a little bit more about that)</p>	<p>Types of information not shared</p> <p>How do you feel about that (sharing/lack of sharing of information?)</p>

<p>If indicated in questionnaire did not know why referred to this HCP explore further</p>	
<p>Thinking about your appointments in general with this health care professional</p> <p>How did you find your appointment(s) with this HCP? Positive/negative (in what way)</p> <p>Did you understand everything that he/she said about your diabetes care? (Yes/No, In what way)</p> <p>How confident/reassured were you about managing your diabetes after seeing this health care professional (in what way?)</p>	<p>Had enough time to discuss your diabetes? Listened to what you had to say? Treated you as a person and not just your condition Felt comfortable discussing your diabetes with her. Were involved in discussions about your diabetes care as much as you wanted to be.</p>
<p>Thinking more generally about all the different health care professionals you see about your diabetes</p> <p>How good are they at communicating/sharing information with one another about you and your diabetes care? (Good/OK/Bad) In what way?</p> <p>How do you feel about that?</p>	<p>Do you think they work well as a team to help you manage your diabetes? Conflicting advice from different HCPs about your diabetes care (informed by questionnaire responses) Yes/No - How do you feel about that? Ever have to repeat same information about your diabetes care to different HCPs (informed by questionnaire response) Yes/No (how do you feel about that?)</p>
<p><u>To finish</u></p> <p>Would you like to be able to continue to attend this service in the future if you need it again?</p> <p>Any way you think service could be improved (Yes/No) In what way?</p>	<p>Why/Why not?</p>